

Teaching In Physics and Mathematics

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Abstract:

Most teachers today are aware that the implementation of interdisciplinary integrated teaching will bring many benefits in the formation and development of action and problem solving capacities for students. Especially Physics, Mathematics, Biology are applied sciences, experimental, is the science of life, knowledge of these subjects is always associated with natural and social factors. Students can use knowledge in many related subjects to solve a number of problems such as: Integrating knowledge of Mathematics to form computational skills, processing data in physics; Physics subject to deal with the physical properties and properties of substances, rays, energy and metabolism; or to easily explain the mechanism of the action of substances on life.

Keywords: *Physics and mathematics*

1. Introduction

The conceptual content "interdisciplinary" can be explained in many different ways. According to the summary report of the 1989 International Conference on Interdisciplinary Science in General Teaching, the concept of interdisciplinarity can be seen as referring to the combination of many subjects. These subjects participate in a common task that allows new knowledge to be generated and developed by their combination.

More specifically, for the level of interaction between subjects, interdisciplinarity ensures a balance in the influence of the subjects. This is a combination of different disciplines dealing with problems whose complexity can only be solved by the convergence and coherence of different perspectives. Thus, in interdisciplinary teaching, we examine a topic, problem or topic by using the method and language of many subjects but with the same aim to develop the learning process in each subject.

Interdisciplinarity in teaching can be done in different ways such as: establishing relationships between school problems; study topics in a subject or topics that make up real-life problems. In addition, it encourages the students' research and research according to their individual interests; teach general concepts and methods that are implemented in situations that involve many different disciplines and do not belong to a particular subject; systematically teaches and imparts methods of thinking and acting in a large set of situations.

To implement interdisciplinary teaching, in practice, it is possible to gather teachers in groups to work with the desire to erase or gradually cross the boundaries of the subjects. At the same time, it is necessary to systematically connect and expand learning activities through competitions and social activities both inside and outside the school.

2. Literature review

2.1. Learners' understanding of derivative and integral concepts

2.1.1. Learners' understanding of derivative concepts

Orton (1983a) was one of the first to conduct research on learners' understanding of the derivative concept. He found that the majority of students and students engaged in experiment proficiency with tasks that required computation or applying familiar processes to solve. However, the learner showed a lack of knowledge about the concept, especially the derivative concept according to the instantaneous rate of variation and the slope of the tangent. Orton argues that the reason is in learners' poor understanding of the limit as well as in the ratio and rate of change.

The lack of recognition of the derivative relationship between the derivative and the variable speed is also confirmed by many other authors (Bezuidenhout, 1998; Bingolbali et al., 2007; Hankiöniemi, 2006; Sahin et al., 2015). For example, Sahin et al. (2015) pointed out that although students know that the formal definition of the derivative is the limit of the difference ratio, it is not possible to explain its relationship to the meaning of the instantaneous rate of variation. Hankiöniemi (2006) also found the difficulty that learners face with the concept of limit to understand how the mean rate of variation approaches the instantaneous rate of variation or how the slope of the sand is gradually approaching the next slope. online.

Thompson (1995), then White and Mitchelmore (1996) found that one of the important reasons for the learner's difficulty with derivative concepts is his understanding of his concept of functions. . They often see only functions as static objects and variables as symbols for manipulation or computation. Meanwhile, according to these authors, the characteristic of the simultaneous variation of the function (the variation of the variable leads to the variation of the function) is the key to developing the understanding of the derivative as speed of change.

Some domestic studies also indicate the lack of perception of high school students with the derivative understanding in the sense of variable speed and functional approximation by tangent (Ngo Minh Duc, 2013; 2016) or difficult. students' problem in connecting different understandings of the derivative to the same concept (Le Thi Hoai Chau, 2014). Besides, a recent study by Le Thi Bach Lien and Tran Kiem Minh (2020) also showed an incomplete understanding of many math pedagogical students about the concept of derivative. This lack of knowledge makes the majority of students in the authors' experiment unable to apply derivatives to successfully solve a problem with a physical context that requires the coordination of physical meaning and geometrical meaning of the knowledge in question. In many documents on analytical derivative in the world, the term "slope" of the line is used with the same connotation as the term "slope coefficient" in math textbooks in Vietnam.

2.1.2. Learners' understanding of integral concepts

Bezuidenhout and Olivier (2000), Jones (2015a, 2015b) conclude that the majority of learners only possess a limited understanding of integral. Typical knowledge learners know are often encapsulated in computational processes according to the primitive value difference or the geometric meaning of the integral as the area of the figure under the curve. Meanwhile, the integral understanding according to the total Riemann term is considered to be the most valuable for understanding the nature and applications of the integral. However, many studies show that learners have a great difficulty understanding integral as the limit of a sum. For example, Rasslan and Tall (2002) examined the understanding of some high school students about the concept of integral. Although these students had an integral approach from the method of approximating the area by sums in the math class, no explanation of the integral related to the limit or the Riemann sum appeared in the math class. experimental results. Instead, students just explain the integral as area, the difference between two primitives or through a specific example of calculation. It seems that the concept of integration according to the total Riemann limit is very difficult to construct or elicit in the learners' perception.

The lack of the Riemann aggregate structure of the integral understanding is even more common among university students as confirmed by the studies of: Orton, 1983b; Jones, 2015b; Sealey, 2014; Wagner, 2017. These authors argue that the reason is due to the complex structure of the integral definition of Riemann's sum as well as the obstacle from another concept - the concept of limit. Another cause is given by Jones et al. (2017) pointed out in the geometric context that traditional analytical textbooks or textbooks use to introduce the concept of integral. He argued that in the context of the problem of the area under the curve, the learner tended to see the Riemann sum as just a process of calculating the area instead of recognizing the nature of the concept behind the calculation method. that math. Furthermore, after the relation between integral and the primitive was established, the area calculation was converted back to a simple process of reversing the derivative. From there, the concept of integral in terms of total Riemannian can gradually become fuzzy and difficult to activate or reinforce in the learner's perception because they do not have any reason to establish such sums.

2.1.3. Difficulty of learners with understanding the relationship between derivative and integral

The inverse relationship between derivative and integral expressed in the fundamental theorem of calculus (from now on will be abbreviated as the fundamental theorem) is one of the most important and useful discoveries of calculus. This theorem works when integrals are defined by the limit of the sum of Riemann. However, in high schools, people often define integral by primitive and according to Bressoud (2011), this makes the basic theorem no longer have any meaning. Kouropatov and Dreyfus (2014) also conclude that most high school students don't know why the primitive can calculate the area, but the reason lies in the basic theorem.

With students having access to the integral of Riemann's sum, the studies of Orton (1983b), Artigue (1991), Thompson (1994b) and Mahir (2009) show that students often only consider basic theorems as a means to compute integral without a clear understanding of the nature of the concepts involved. They could not explain the inverse relationship between derivative and integral nor why a quantity determined by the total Riemann limit can be calculated in primitive terms.

Difficulty in understanding the basic theorem according to Thompson (1994b) stems from the 'poor conception of the rate of variation and from the lack of conception of a function as a simultaneous variation of two quantities. "(P. 2). Or to broadly say it stems from the lack of understanding of related concepts such as derivative, integral, function, limit.

Difficulty with the basic theorem is also shown in presenting a strict proof for it, especially for high school students. In order to have such a rigorous proof in history, mathematicians have faced "scientific stumbling blocks" as indicated in Klisinska's (2009) doctoral thesis. The results of this thesis show that, although there have been many different versions of proofs appearing in general or tertiary derivative institutions, the aforementioned obstacles always cause great difficulties for learners in their work. understand the meaning of the basic theorem as well as how to prove it.

2.2. Research towards teaching derivative and integral to support their application in Physics

2.2.1. Teaching derivative concepts for application in Physics

Many studies have shown that learners have difficulty using derivatives in physics problems (Beichner, 1994; Bingolbali et al., 2007; Jones, 2017). The main reason according to Jones (2017) is that the analytic derivative program emphasizes more on the geometric meaning of the derivative (tangential coefficients), while the applied context of Physics mainly uses using variable speed interpretation. This mismatched coupling creates a gap between learning the derivative and understanding its effective applications in physics. This statement is also supported by research by Dray et al. (2008) when they showed that to bridge the gap between Math and Physics, the central idea of the derivative concept should be the rate of variation rather than the coefficient of tangent angles.

There is a great deal of derivative work associated with applications in physics, but most focus on the dynamic context involving the three quantities of distance, speed and acceleration. However, according to the conclusion of Thompson (1994a; 1994b) and Bezuidenhout (1998), it seems that the dynamic context does not help students fully understand the meaning of the rate of variation. students simply understand that the derivative is used to calculate velocity or acceleration without expanding the understanding of the rate of variation for quantities outside the dynamic context or even the variable quantities. by the time. Jones (2017) concludes that overfocusing on the applications of the derivative in the kinetic context may not provide a complete understanding of the derivative so that it can be used in many other contexts of the derivative. Physics.

One of our studies (Ngo Minh Duc, 2016) shows that students' conception of derivative is not enough to understand its diverse applications in the many problems of high school physics. To be able to understand the application of derivative in these physics problems, students need to grasp how to understand the derivative in

terms of the instantaneous rate of variation and the idea of approximating a function derivative by the tangent of the line. curved corresponding to it.

2.2.2. Teaching integral concepts for application in Physics

The research of Thompson and Silverman (2008), Jones (2015a) shows that understanding integral in terms of primitives or areas under curves is not enough to explain the applications of integral in non-mathematical contexts. in general and physics in particular. For example, when looking at the physics and engineering textbooks, Jones (2015b) found that the integral interpretation of primitives has little activity in the definition and calculation of physical quantities. In the author's words, the primitive integral explanation "does not provide the expected meaning in physics and engineering" (p. 10). In addition, the understanding of integral by area is also not enough to effectively support the applications of integrals in physics because learners have difficulty recognizing the area under the curve to represent the quantity. physics (Nguyen Dong Hai & Rebello, 2011).

Thompson and Silverman (2008) suggest a way to help learners understand the area under the curve when it represents a quantity other than area such as distance or force of force. It is to understand the process of integrating as an accumulation of (summing) small increments made up of the products - which is based on the structure of Riemann's sum. Likewise, according to Jones (2015a), the primitive integral has lessened the meaning of integral in the applied context, and he also argues that the integral interpretation of the Riemann sum should be stimulated. works in the learner if he wants to apply integration in many problems of physics. Regarding teaching integrals to connect with applications in physics, Dray et al. (2008) also suggested that the central idea of integral should be based on the Riemann sum structure (subdivide, multiply, add, and pass through the limit) instead of the area under the curve. Most studies in this direction confirm that the Riemann total integral is most valuable for understanding the applications of integral in contexts, especially physics (Jones, 2015a, 2015b. ; Sealey 2006; 2014; Thompson & Silverman, 2008).

Another difficulty that learners encounter when applying integration to Physics does not come from the lack of knowledge of mathematics or physics but from the form of "isolated" knowledge they possess. In other words, the derivative of Mathematics and Physics, if taking place separately, can limit the ability to apply mathematical knowledge to the contexts of the remaining subjects. In particular, with the concept of integral, the approach from the area calculation helps learners realize the subdivision, building product and summing up to approximate the area under the curve. However, they may have difficulty applying the Riemann total area method to another unfamiliar context such as the problem of determining distance or the force of force. This statement is confirmed by studies of Rebello (2007) and Bajracharya (2014) or in one of our studies (Ngo Minh Duc, 2019) when experimental students show that they have enough knowledge. equipment but still have difficulty in applying it to physics problems.

2.3. Research on using physics to support the teaching of the concepts of calculus

The basic concepts of calculus such as derivative and integral have a close relation of meaning to many physical quantities such as work, distance, velocity, acceleration, ... Priority of these quantities in real life or studying Physics can assist learners to better understand the abstract concepts of calculus. Marrongelle's (2001, 2004, 2010) studies have called for the use of knowledge and context from physics to construct meaningful notions for analytic concepts such as derivative or integral.

Firouzian and Speer (2015) provide a classification scheme of the uses of physics to aid in learning the concepts of calculus including: contextization (using physical context as a medium). to solve problems), illustrations (suggest examples from physics to help understand the concepts and problems of analysis), language - mix (using a combination of the language of Mathematics and Physics), and ultimately not in use.

Some other authors studying the derivative linking calculus with Physics have proposed several theories such as "cognitive fusion" (Fauconnier & Turner, 2002) or "cognitive resources" (Hammer, 2000). These theoretical

prisms allow learners to understand how learners use mathematics to solve physics problems or use insights from physics to develop awareness of a mathematical concept.

2.4. Mathematics and Physics inter-subject teaching programs

2.4.1. At the university level

Các khóa học liên môn Toán – Vật lý nhằm thúc đẩy việc dạy học giải tích đã được xây dựng và deployed in many universities around the world. Examples include the Interdisciplinary Course of Analysis and Physics at the University of Hampshire (Marrongelle, 2001), integrating analysis with science at the Louisiana Technical University (Carpenter et al., 2007), Math Integration Program - Physics of the Tecnologico de Monterrey University (Domínguez et al., 2015). These interdisciplinary programs are designed to teach science or economics students who will need analytical knowledge in their area of expertise.

In the aforementioned courses, concepts like derivative and integral will be taught alternately and in conjunction with physics lessons or some lab sessions. Contexts, models, and experience gained from the physics class will assist learners in understanding the concepts of calculus. At the same time, these concepts will then become effective tools to solve the problems posed in physics.

2.4.2. At the high school level

The study of analytical derivative in general and the interdisciplinary point of view in particular in high schools has not received much attention from the research community of math education in the world. In a review of the problem of analytic derivative work in European high schools, Törner et al. (2014) found that the research works on this topic are very little and limited compared with similar studies at the graduate derivative level. The authors explain this probably because the traditional derivatives in high school are too far from the goal of helping students understand the complex concepts of calculus as well as apply them effectively. in non-math contexts.

In high schools, Math is often taught independently and rarely appears interdisciplinary programs with other subjects. However, when referring to a review of the analytical derivative Bressoud et al. (2016), we recognize that interdisciplinary trends have had a certain influence in the design of analytical derivative programs for high school students in many countries around the world in recent years. This is reflected in a greater emphasis on diverse applications of calculus in other disciplines, especially Physics. Even in some countries (such as Korea or Singapore), programmers have determined that analysis must be started early to prepare research tools for Physics and other fields. . Some authors (Thompson, 1994a; Turner et al., 2000) also propose to introduce important ideas of analysis such as the concept of rate of change from the lower secondary level to prepare the premise for understanding and applying the concept of derivative later. They argue that many important ideas of calculus can be introduced early enough to students through life or physics experiences in preparation for an understanding of mathematical concepts in higher level of education.

2.5. Research on teaching analytics from an interdisciplinary point of view in Vietnam

Although the derivative trend according to the integrated - interdisciplinary point of view has been interested and studied in Vietnam in recent decades, however, we found that the research works on the subject of interdisciplinary Mathematics and Science Studying very little and mainly focused on the dimension of applying math. In particular, the research direction on derivative of applying mathematics to practical and scientific problems has been interested for a long time, but considering it from the perspective of integration - interdisciplinary work has only been done. Here in some works. One of them is the research of author Nguyen The Son (2017) on the topic of building math integration topics. In his doctoral thesis, the author has proposed processes and measures to assist teachers in designing and deriving topics that integrate math with content of other subjects in high school. Many interdisciplinary learning activities are also built in this project and often focus on the application of math knowledge in problems of other sciences such as Physics, Chemistry, Biology,

... This interdisciplinary approach helps highlight the role of math tools in solving practical and scientific problems. In addition, there are a number of other studies also going in a similar direction when connecting mathematical knowledge with interdisciplinary problems, such as geometric derivative associated with practical problems and physics (Dao Tam and Pham Van Effect, 2018) or apply knowledge of probability and statistics in genetic problems (Nguyen Thi Ha, 2016). However, in general, the above mentioned works still do not pay attention to the opposite impact direction, showing the support of the sciences in helping to better understand mathematical knowledge as well as the reciprocal connection between the subjects. the subject to derive an appropriate knowledge content in an interdisciplinary orientation.

Also from an interdisciplinary point of view, but considering the learners' ability to solve interdisciplinary problems. The research of author Tran Van Hoc (2018) with high school students and Le Thi Hoai Chau and Ngo Minh Duc (2018) with students of Pedagogical School also shows that learners have difficulty in solving. solve problems that require applying knowledge from both mathematics and physics, in particular with the concept of integration. Another study that explores teachers' conceptions of the interdisciplinary between Mathematics and Physics related to the vector topic was done by Nguyen Thi Nga (2018). The results show that math teachers are less interested in the applications of vectors in Physics and do not relate these applications to help students better understand the concept of mathematics.

For the research on analytical derivatives in the country, we find some works of the authors: Trinh Thi Bach Tuyet (2016), Pham Si Nam (2013), Nguyen Phu Loc (2006), Tran Anh Dung (2013). These works study the derivative of the concepts of calculus in high schools in the direction of activating learning activities and developing learners' competencies, but none of these works from the perspective of inter-math with subjects. Science in general, Physics in particular.

3. Conclusion and research orientation

The review results of the literature show a double difficulty of learners both in understanding derivative and integral concepts as well as in using them to solve problems with physical contexts. In many cases, it is the lack of conceptual understanding that causes the difficulties in their application. Many studies have shown that learners have difficulty understanding the derivative of the rate of variation and the integral of the total Riemann limit as well as the inverse relationship between these two concepts. Yet these insights are most useful for applying derivatives and integrals to various problems of physics and practice. For that reason, many authors propose a greater emphasis on the two above understandings to make a connection between the derivative of analysis and its application in Physics.

Other studies look at ways and schemes that allow physics to be used to aid in understanding analytic concepts. Some authors also call for examining the evolutionary history of calculus to see the disciplined connections between it and physics and to make use of them in derivative work at school.

The general study also shows that researches in the world on analytical derivative in general, analytical derivative towards interdisciplinary approach in particular mainly focus on students of universities. and college. The research on derivative, integral and derivative for high school students with the orientation of Math and Physics interdisciplinary has not received adequate attention. Moreover, there are not many studies in the interdisciplinary direction, which take into account the articulation of the curriculum content and the reciprocal effects between the derivative of Mathematics and Physics in high schools.

In Vietnam, the trend of interdisciplinary integration in education is currently receiving a lot of research interest. However, the interdisciplinary approach in Math derivative has its own characteristics and still needs more research to keep up with world trends and to apply appropriately to the domestic situation. Some works in the country have discussed the analytical derivative for high school students, but not from the point of view of the interdisciplinary derivative. Many other works study the general theoretical problems of Math derivative from the point of view of integration or proceed to build some derivative topics integrating mathematics with

sciences. However, in general, there is still no research on derivative of derivative and integral concepts in the direction of taking advantage of the interconnections of Mathematics and Physics placed in the coupling between the ethical institutions. the high school function aims to bring more benefits to both subjects. Based on the results obtained from the review and review of the derived question “how to take advantage of the interdisciplinary connections between Mathematics and Physics in analytic derivatives in high schools to help students Overcoming the difficulties in understanding the abstract concepts of calculus, and applying analysis to the problems of Physics? ”, we propose the following research orientation: The relationship between analysis and physics has been shown in the history of formation and development of two concepts of derivative and integral. Then will test how this interdisciplinary relationship has shown in the content of mathematics and physics curriculum in high school? What conceptual understandings need to be formed in learners, what articulation must ensure for interdisciplinary derivative work to take place more effectively and appropriately? The results from this analysis are the basis for us to propose pedagogical measures to take advantage of the links in Math - Physics to help learners better understand the two concepts of derivative and integral simultaneously. use them in many problems of Physics.

References

- i Akkoç, H., Bingolbali, E., & Ozmantar, F. (2008). *Investigating the technological pedagogical content knowledge: A case of derivative at a point*. In *Proceedings of the Joint Meeting of the 32nd Conference of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education, and the XXX North American Chapter*(Vol. 2, pp. 17-24).
- ii Anderson, L. W., Krathwohl, D. R., Airasian, P. W., Cruikshank, K. A., Mayer, R. E., Pintrich, P. R., ... & Wittrock, M. C. (2001). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives, abridged edition*. White Plains, NY: Longman.
- iii Artigue, M. (2000). *Didactic engineering and the complexity of learning processes in classroom situations*. In C. Bergsten, G. Dahland, & B. Grevholm (Eds.), *Proceedings of the MADIF 2 Conference* (pp. 5–20). Gothenburg: Swedish Society for Research in Mathematics Education
- iv Artigue, M. (2014). *Didactic engineering in mathematics education*. *Encyclopedia of mathematics education*, 159-162.
- v Bajracharya, R. R. (2014). *Student application of the fundamental theorem of calculus with graphical representations in mathematics and physics*.
- vi Bajracharya, R., & Thompson, J. R. (2014). *Student understanding of the fundamental theorem of calculus at the mathematics-physics interface*. *Proceedings of the 17th special interest group of the Mathematical Association of America on research in undergraduate mathematics education*. Denver (CO).
- vii Beichner, R. J. (1994). *Testing student interpretation of kinematics graphs*. *American journal of Physics*, 62(8), 750-762.
- viii Berlin, D. F., & White, A. L. (1992). *Report from the NSF/SSMA Wingspread conference: A network for integrated science and mathematics teaching and learning*. *School science and mathematics*, 92(6), 340-342.
- ix Berlin, D. F., & White, A. L. (1994). *The Berlin-White integrated science and mathematics model*. *School Science and Mathematics*, 94(1), 2-4.
- x Berlin, D. F. (2007). *Using a Cultural Context to Integrate Mathematics and Science Education*. *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference Mathematics Education in a Global Community*, 84-88.
- xi Bezuidenhout, J. (1998). *First-year university students' understanding of rate of change*. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 29(3), 389-399.
- xii Bezuidenhout, J., & Olivier, A. (2000, July). *Students' conceptions of the integral*. In *PME CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, pp. 2-73).

- xiii Bingolbali, E., Monaghan, J., & Roper, T. (2007). *Engineering students' conceptions of the derivative and some implications for their mathematical education*. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 38(6), 763-777.
- xiv Boyer, C. B. (1959). *The history of the calculus and its conceptual development:(The concepts of the calculus)*. Courier Corporation.
- xv Bosch, M., & Chevallard, Y. (1999). *La sensibilité de l'activité mathématique aux ostensifs: objet d'étude et problématique*. *Recherches en didactique des mathématiques (Revue)*, 19(1), 77-123.
- xvi Bressoud, D. M. (2011). *Historical reflections on teaching the fundamental theorem of integral calculus*. *The American Mathematical Monthly*, 118(2), 99-115.
- xvii Brousseau, G. (2006). *Theory of didactical situations in mathematics: Didactique des mathématiques, 1970–1990 (Vol. 19)*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- xviii Brousseau, G. (2008). *Research in mathematics education*. In M. Niss (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 10th international congress on mathematical education* (pp. 244–254). IMFUFA: Denmark.
- xix Chevallard, Y. (1985). *La transposition didactique*. Grenoble. *La pensée sauvage*.
- xx Chevallard, Y. (1989, August). *On didactic transposition theory: Some introductory notes*. In *Proceedings of The International Symposium on Selected Domains of Research and Development in Mathematics Education*. Bratislava.
- xxi Chevallard, Y. (1992). *Fundamental concepts in didactics: perspectives provided by an anthropological approach*. *Research in didactique of mathematics: Selected papers*, 131-168.
- xxii D'Hainaut, L. (1986, May). *Interdisciplinarity in general education*. In *International Symposium on Interdisciplinarity in General Education*, UNESCO.
- xxiii Doorman, M., & Van Maanen, J. (2008). *A historical perspective on teaching and learning calculus*. *Australian Senior Mathematics Journal*, 22(2), 4.
- xxiv Douglas, R. G. (1986). *Toward a lean and lively calculus: conference/workshop to develop alternative curriculum and teaching methods for calculus at the college level*, Tulane University, January 2-6, 1986 (Vol. 6). *Mathematical Assn of Amer Drake, S. M., & Burns, R. C. (2004). Meeting standards through integrated curriculum*. ASCD.
- xxv Drake, S. M. (2007). *Creating Standards-Based Integrated Curriculum: Aligning Curriculum, Content, Assessment, and Instruction*. Corwin Press, A SAGE Publications Company. 2455 Teller Road, Thousand Oaks, CA 91320.
- xxvi Dray, T., Edwards, B., & Manogue, C. A. (2008, July). *Bridging the gap between mathematics and physics*. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Congress on Mathematics Education*.
- xxvii Duval, R. (2006). *A cognitive analysis of problems of comprehension in a learning of mathematics*. *Educational studies in mathematics*, 61(1-2), 103-131.
- xxviii Đỗ Hương Trà. (2015). *Nghiên cứu dạy học tích hợp liên môn: những yêu cầu đặt ra trong việc xây dựng, lựa chọn nội dung và tổ chức dạy học*. *VNU Journal of Science: Education Research*, 31(1).
- xxix Education Development Center. (1970). *Final report of Cambridge Conference on School Mathematics, January 1962 – August 1970*. Cambridge, MA: Author.
- xxx Edwards, C. J. (2012). *The historical development of the calculus*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- xxxii Eves, H. W. (1976). *An introduction to the history of mathematics*.
- xxxiii Fauconnier, G. T., & Turner, M. (2002). *M.(2002) The way we think: conceptual blending and the mind's hidden complexities*.
- xxxiv Ferrini-Mundy, J., & Graham, K. (1994). *Research in calculus learning: Understanding of limits, derivatives, and integrals*. *MAA notes*, 31-46.
- xxxv Fikhtengol'ts, G. M. (1965). *The fundamentals of mathematical analysis*. Elsevier. Pergamon Press.
- xxxv Firouzian, S. S. (2013). *Students' way of thinking about derivative and its correlation to their ways of solving applied problems*. In *Proceedings of the 16th Annual conference on research in undergraduate mathematics Education* (pp. 492-497).

- xxxvi Firouzian, S., & Speer, N. (2015). *Integrated mathematics and science knowledge for teaching framework*. In *Proceedings of the Proceedings of the 18th conference on Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*.
- xxxvii Frykholm, J., & Glasson, G. (2005). *Connecting science and mathematics instruction: Pedagogical context knowledge for teachers*. *School Science and Mathematics*, 105(3), 127-141.
- xxxviii González-Martín, A. S., Bloch, I., Durand-Guerrier, V., & Maschietto, M. (2014). *Didactic Situations and Didactical Engineering in university mathematics: cases from the study of Calculus and proof*. *Research in Mathematics Education*, 16(2), 117-134.
- xxxix Grabiner, J. V. (1983). *The changing concept of change: The derivative from Fermat to Weierstrass*. *Mathematics Magazine*, 56(4), 195-206.
- xl Gravemeijer, K., & Doorman, M. (1999). *Context problems in realistic mathematics education: A calculus course as an example*. *Educational studies in mathematics*, 39(1-3), 111-129.
- xli Habineza, F. (2013). *A case study of analyzing student teachers' concept images of the definite integral*. *Rwandan Journal of Education*, 1(2), 38-54.
- xlii Hammer, D. (2000). *Student resources for learning introductory physics*. *American Journal of Physics*, 68(S1), S52-S59.
- xliii Hiebert, J., & Lefevre, P. (1986). *Conceptual and procedural knowledge in mathematics: An introductory analysis*. *Conceptual and procedural knowledge: The case of mathematics*, 2, 1-27.
- xliv Hiebert, J., & Carpenter, T. P. (1992). *Learning and teaching with understanding*. *Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning: A project of the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics*, 65-97.
- xlv Huntley, M. A. (1998). *Theoretical and Empirical Investigations of Integrated Mathematics and Science Education in the Middle Grades*.
- xlvi Hurley, M. M. (2001). *Reviewing integrated science and mathematics: The search for evidence and definitions from new perspectives*. *School science and mathematics*, 101(5), 259-268.
- xlvii Jacobs, H. H. (1989). *Interdisciplinary curriculum: Design and implementation*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development, 1250 N. Pitt Street, Alexandria, VA 22314.
- xlviii Jones, S. R. (2010). *Applying Mathematics to Physics and Engineering: Symbolic Forms of the Integral (Doctoral dissertation)*.
- xlix Jones, S. R. (2015a). *Areas, anti-derivatives, and adding up pieces: Definite integrals in pure mathematics and applied science contexts*. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 38, 9-28.
- l Jones, S. R. (2015b). *The prevalence of area-under-a-curve and anti-derivative conceptions over Riemann sum-based conceptions in students' explanations of definite integrals*. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 46(5), 721-736.
- li Jones, S. R. (2017). *An exploratory study on student understandings of derivatives in real-world, non-kinematics contexts*. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 45, 95-110.
- lii Jones, S. R., Lim, Y., & Chandler, K. R. (2017). *Teaching integration: How certain instructional moves may undermine the potential conceptual value of the Riemann sum and the Riemann integral*. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 15(6), 1075-1095.
- liii Kaput, J. (1994). *Democratizing access to calculus: New routes to old roots*. *Mathematical thinking and problem solving*, 77-156.
- liv Katz, V. J. (2000). *Using history to teach mathematics: An international perspective (Vol. 51)*. Cambridge University Press.
- lv Kendal, M., & Stacey, K. (2003). *Tracing learning of three representations with the differentiation competency framework*. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 15(1), 22-41.
- lvi Kleiner, I. (2001). *History of the infinitely small and the infinitely large in calculus*. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 48(2-3), 137-174.

- lvii Kouropatov, A., & Dreyfus, T. (2013). *Constructing the integral concept on the basis of the idea of accumulation: suggestion for a high school curriculum. International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 44(5), 641-651.
- lviii Le Thi Bach Lien., & Tran Kiem Minh. (2020). *Knowledge of content pedagogy of future math teachers in Vietnam when teaching derivative topics. Journal of Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education*, 17 (8), 1410.
- lix Le Thi Hoai Chau., & Tran Thi My Dung. (2004). *Integral and differential calculations in history. Journal of Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education*, (4), 14.
- lx Le Thi Hoai Chau. (2004). *Exploit the history of Mathematics in teaching integral concepts. Journal of Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education*, (2), 37-45.
- lxi Le Thi Hoai Chau. (2014). *Modeling in teaching derivative concepts. Journal of Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education*, (65), 5-18.
- lxii Le Thi Hoai Chau. (2017). *Proceedings of the 6th International Workshop on Didactic Mathematics. The necessity of epistemological analysis for the researches on teaching activities and teacher training (pp.17-38). Ho Chi Minh City: HCMC University of Education Publishing House.*
- lxiii Le Thi Hoai Chau. (2018). *Anthropology in Didactic Mathematics. Ho Chi Minh City: Ho Chi Minh City University of Education Press*
- lxiv Le Thi Hoai Chau., & Ngo Minh Duc. (2019). *Training mathematics teachers in accordance with teaching to integrated math and science through teaching integration concept. Vietnam Journal of Education*, 6, 48-53.
- lxv Loepf, F. L. (1999). *Models of curriculum integration. The journal of technology studies*, 25(2), 21-25.
- lxvi Lonning, R. A., & DeFranco, T. C. (1997). *Integration of science and mathematics: A theoretical model. School science and mathematics*, 97(4), 212-215.
- lxvii Mathison, S., & Freeman, M. (1998). *The Logic of Interdisciplinary Studies. Report Series 2.33.*
- lxviii Marrongelle, K. A. (2001). *Physics experiences and calculus: How students use physics to construct meaningful conceptualizations of calculus concepts in an interdisciplinary calculus/physics course.*
- lxix Marrongelle, K. A. (2004). *How students use physics to reason about calculus tasks. School Science and Mathematics*, 104(6), 258-272.
- lxx Marrongelle, K. (2010, March). *The role of physics in students' conceptualization of calculus concepts: Implications of research on teaching practice. In 2nd International Conference on the Teaching of Mathematics.*
- lxxi Meredith, D. C., & Marrongelle, K. A. (2008). *How students use mathematical resources in an electrostatics context. American Journal of Physics*, 76(6), 570-578.
- lxxii National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (Ed.). (2000). *Principles and standards for school mathematics (Vol. 1). National Council of Teachers of*
- lxxiii Ngo Minh Duc. (two thousand and thirteen). *Derivative concept in teaching Mathematics and Physics in high schools (Master thesis, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education).*
- lxxiv Ngo Minh Duc. (2016). *Teaching derivative concepts in relation to subjects with physics. Journal of Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education*, (7 (85)), 41.
- lxxv Ngo Minh Duc. (2017). *Integrated perspective in teaching integral concepts. Journal of Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education*, 14 (4), 20-28.
- lxxvi Ngo Minh Duc. (2017). *Consider the pedagogical transformation of the concept of integral in connection with physics at high schools in Vietnam. Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Didactic Mathematics (pp.103-112). Ho Chi Minh City: HCMC University of Education Publishing House.*
- lxxvii Nguyen, D. H., & Rebello, N. S. (2011). *Students' understanding and application of the area under the curve concept in physics problems. Physical Review Special Topics- Physics Education Research*, 7 (1), 010112

- lxxviii Nguyen Phu Loc. (2006). *Improve the efficiency of teaching calculus in high schools in the direction of approaching some problems of mathematical methodology*. Education Science Doctoral Thesis. Vinh University.
- lxxix Nguyen The Son. (2017). *Building integrated topics in teaching math in high school*. Education Science Doctoral Thesis. Vietnam Institute of Educational Science.
- lxxx Nguyen Thi Ha. (2016). *Integrating Mathematics in guiding students to solve Genetic problems (Biology 12)*. Journal of Science, Hanoi National University, 32 (1), 68- 72.
- lxxxi Nguyen Thi Nga. (2018). *Mathematics - Physics interdisciplinary in teaching vector topics in high schools: Researching personal relationships of teachers of Mathematics and Physics*. Journal of Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Education, 15 (1), 40-47.
- lxxxii Nikitina, S., & Mansilla, V. B. (2003). *Three strategies for interdisciplinary math and science teaching: A case of the Illinois Mathematics and Science Academy*. Project Zero, the Harvard Graduate School of Education-Interdisciplinary Studies Project, 1-21.
- lxxxiii López-Gay, R., Sáez, J. M., & Torregrosa, J. M. (2015). *Obstacles to mathematization in physics: The case of the differential*. Science & Education, 24 (5-6), 591-613.
- lxxxiv Oliveira, A. R. E. (2014). *A History of the Work Concept*. Springer.
- lxxxv Orton, A. (1983a) *Students' understanding of differentiation*. Educational studies in mathematics, 14 (3), 235-250.
- lxxxvi Orton, A. (1983b). *Students' understanding of integration*. Educational studies in mathematics, 14 (1), 1-18.
- lxxxvii Pape, S. J., & Tchoshanov, M. A. (2001). *The role of representation (s) in developing mathematical understanding*. Theory into practice, 40 (2), 118-127.
- lxxxviii Perkins, D. (2012). *Calculus and its origins*. MAA.
- lxxxix Pham Si Nam. (two thousand and thirteen). *Improve the effectiveness of teaching a number of analytical concepts for high school students specializing in Mathematics on the basis of applying constructivist theory*. Education Science Doctoral Thesis. Vinh University.
- xc Piaget, J., & Cook, M. (1952). *The origins of intelligence in children* (Vol. 8, No. 5, p.18). New York: International Universities Press.
- xci Roegiers, X. (2001). *Une pédagogie de l'intégration: compétences et intégration des acquis dans l'enseignement*. De Boeck Supérieur.
- xcii Roundy, D., Dray, T., Manogue, C. A., Wagner, J. F., & Weber, E. (2014). *An extended theoretical framework for the concept of derivative*. In Proceedings of the 18th Annual Conference on Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education (pp. 838-843).
- xciii Sahin, Z., Yenmez, A. A., & Erbas, A. K. (2015). *Relational Understanding of the Derivative Concept through Mathematical Modeling: A Case Study*. Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education, 11(1).
- xciv Stillwell, J. (2002). *Mathematics and its History*. The Australian Mathem. Soc, 168.
- xcv Tall, D., & Vinner, S. (1981). *Concept image and concept definition in mathematics with particular reference to limits and continuity*. Educational studies in mathematics, 12(2), 151-169.
- xcvi Tall, D. (Ed.). (1991). *Advanced mathematical thinking* (Vol. 11). Springer Science & Business Media.
- xcvii Tall, D. (1993). *Students' difficulties in calculus*. In proceedings of working group (Vol.3, pp. 13-28).
- xcviii Thompson, P. W. (1994a). *The development of the concept of speed and its relationship to concepts of rate. The development of multiplicative reasoning in the learning of mathematics*, 179-234.
- xcix Thompson, P. W. (1994b). *Images of rate and operational understanding of the fundamental theorem of calculus*. Educational studies in mathematics, 26(2-3), 229-274.